

Paramagnetic Resonance in Gamma Irradiated Chloramine-T

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Chloramine-T ($P\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NCl Na}$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) has considerable use as a mild oxidizing agent¹ for a variety of reductants. There are conflicting reports about its thermal and photochemical stability in the solid state². This prompted us to investigate the effect of Cu-K α X-rays and Co⁶⁰-gamma rays on solid Chloramine-T³. Intense decomposition of the compound occurred upon exposure to these radiations, the magnitude of decomposition being followed by determining its loss of oxidizing power in aqueous solution. The number of molecules decomposing per 100 ev of radiant energy, $G_{(-CAT)}$, was found to be around 300, indicating the operation of chain factors in the various steps of decomposition. In this context, it was found to be of interest to record the e.s.r. spectrum of gamma irradiated anhydrous and hydrate forms of chloramine-T, to detect the presence of any free radical species, produced under irradiation.

Merck reagent grade Chloramine-T was purified by further recrystallization from aqueous solution. The anhydrous salt was obtained by drying the hydrate between 70–80° for 18 hrs.

The microcrystalline hydrate and anhydrous compounds were sealed in pyrex glass tubes in presence of air and were irradiated in a 11500 curie 220 Gamma Cell, the dose rate of which was determined with a Fricke Dosimeter. The e.s.r. spectra of the gamma irradiated salts were obtained with Varian Associates V 4502-EPR spectrometer equipped with an X-band microwave bridge and a V-4531 cavity. The samples were taken in 3 mm (O.D.) quartz tubes sealed under nitrogen. The frequency was calibrated with a Hewlett-packard frequency counter and the magnetic field was accurately standardized with a proton probe. A field modulation of 100 KC/S was used.

The e.s.r. spectra (first derivative plots of the absorption curve) of the irradiated compounds drawn at room temperature are shown in Fig. 1. They consist of single absorption lines and are slightly asymmetric. The g-tensors for the cross over points measured by inserting polycrystalline DPPH as internal standard and line widths ΔM s obtained for the spectra are given in Table I. No hyperfine splitting was obtained even under maximum resolution.

The slight asymmetry noticed in the derivative spectra can be attributed to the random orientations of the radicals in the irradiated material. This could result in g anisotropy.

1. Volumetric Analysis, Vol. III, Editors : I. M. Kolthoff and R., Belcher, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1957, p. 639.
2. E. Bishop and V. J. Jennings, *Talanta*, 1958, 1, 197.
3. D. S. Mahadevappa and A. S. Ananda Murthy, Unpublished results.

Evaluation of anisotropic g tensors from powder e.s.r. spectra has been discussed by several workers⁴⁻⁷. These involve calculation of theoretical line shapes employing computer fits,

Fig. 1. The e.s.r. spectra of gamma irradiated Chloramine-T.

(I) $p\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NCl Na}$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and

(II) $p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NCl Na}$

The vertical line indicates the position of DPPH.

The magnetic field increases from left to right.

but approximate calculations of g tensors can be done from the derivative spectra by the method suggested by Poole⁸. These are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Total dose absorbed ev/gm	g	Δms^* (Gauss)	g_1	g_2	g_3
$P\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NClNa}$ $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.86×10^{19}	2.006	25.0	2.014	2.006	2.000
$P\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NClNa}$	2.74×10^{19}	2.0036**	11.6	2.006	2.0036	2.000

* Width between points of maximum slope taken from the first derivative of the e.s.r. spectrum.

** Resonance lines of anhydrous compound and DPPH ($g = 2.0036$) overlap.

A positive identification of the free radical produced in gamma irradiated Chloramine-T may prove to be difficult, but some tentative comments can be made regarding the nature of those paramagnetic centers. The reported g values are slightly greater than the free spin value of 2.0023. Although the spectra are drawn at a single microwave frequency, the g factors indicate that there is more or less a complete quenching of orbital momentum in the free radicals, resulting in little spin-orbit coupling. Absence of hyperfine interaction clearly indicates that the paramagnetic electron is not strongly involved with the spin nuclei in the aromatic ring or in the side chain. It is likely that the Dirac delta function of the spin Hamiltonian is zero, with no electron density on any of the non-zero spin nuclei. It may therefore be concluded that the odd electron is moving in a delocalized II orbital.

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- F. Kneubuhl, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, **33**, 1074.
- R. P. Kohin and C. P. Poole Jr., *Bull. Ann. Phys. Soc. II*, 1958, **3**, 8.
- J. A. Ibers and J. D. Swalen, *Phys. Rev.*, 1962, **127**, 1914.
- T. S. Johnston and H. G. Hecht, *J. Mol. Spectroscopy*, 1965, **17**, 98.
- C. P. Poole Jr, 'Electron spin Resonance'; p. 830-832, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1967.